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D2.6: Legal Requirements

WP2

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1. Introduction

The LIFE WEEELOOP project proposes a new holistic management system for Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), based on circular economy models particularly focused on the recovery of materials and components of kitchen hobs (induction, radiant and hybrid) achieving a recovery rate of 90%.

The proper recycling of WEEE and the recovery of valuable components and materials is essential for both environmental protection and economic sustainability. Incorrect disposal of electronic waste can release harmful toxins into ecosystems, which poses significant risks to human health and biodiversity. Recovery and Recycling WEEE responsibly can help mitigate these dangers by conserving valuable resources and reducing the need for mining and raw material extraction. The LIFE WEEELOOP project introduces innovative recovery processes, improving the efficiency of WEEE recycling by enabling the extraction of metals, plastics, and rare earth elements while minimizing energy consumption and waste production. These advancements not only enhance recycling outcomes but also contribute to a more sustainable waste management system.

In order to accomplish its objectives a key element is to define all requirements affecting the operations to be performed which is addressed in Work Package WP2 “Requirements specifications & permits for process and industrialisation”. This Work Package includes specifically the analysis of the legislation and regulations to be met in the management of the WEEE, that is addressed in this Deliverable D2.6. “Legal Requirements”. Nevertheless, this summary represents an overview of key legal requirements related to waste management operations and it does not replace or supersede official legal texts, which remain the authoritative sources. Organizations must ensure compliance with all applicable laws and regulations and conditions established in their Authorizations by consulting the relevant legal documents.

Work package WP2 – Requirements specifications & permits for process and industrialisation

Work Package Number	WP2	Lead Beneficiary	2 - REPLAY
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Objectives
<p>The aim of WP2 is the definition of all project requirements including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of the process technical requirements for the development of the Circular AI platform. • Definition of process logistics and supply. • Definition of protocols for components and materials recovery. • Definition of technical specifications for recovered components and materials. • Definition of Digital Passport specifications for recovered components and materials and for the European Digital Product Passport for the new product. • Industrialisation requirements definition for the developed eco-designed product.

2. Objective and Scope

This Deliverable intends to summarize the major environmental and safety legislative or regulatory requirements affecting waste management that must be taken into account in the operations to be performed in the project as outlined in the Grant Agreement

Deliverable D2.6 – Legal requirements

Deliverable Number	D2.6	Lead Beneficiary	5 - ECOLEC (EEAR)
Deliverable Name	Legal requirements		
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Description
<p>Legal requirements to be taken into account by each actor including, collection, handling, transportation, preparation for reuse or recovery and documentation or reporting.</p> <p>The report covers potential project-affecting future developments and related areas like managing obsolete inventory, circularity, reparability, measures against obsolescence and waste management info in Digital Product Passports. ECOLEC (EEAR) will update quarterly and alert the Consortium of new developments.</p> <p>Electronic format. English.</p>

and therefore specifically:

- General Waste and WEEE specific legislation
- Obligations to and responsibilities of the different actors
- Eco-design requirements affecting end-of-life management
- Prevention of waste and extension of the life of the product
- Collection
- Handling
- Transportation
- Preparing for Reuse
- Recovery operations: Recycling
- Documentation

Given the nature of this document, it cannot pretend to be an exhaustive description of all the regulatory requirements affecting each operation at each geographical location and for each actor. It intends to be a summary of the major legislation with the key aspects to be taken into account. Moreover, since legal requirements may vary depending on the Autonomous Regions (in Spanish, *Comunidades Autónomas*) or even at local level based on e.g. local ordinances; the document will focus on the more generic instances of wider application.

Furthermore, since as a general rule, any actor managing waste must have the necessary Authorizations issued by the competent authorities, mainly Regional or Local, they should operate within the regulatory schemes governing their operations.

In any case, since the level of understanding and control on the different topics will evolve during the Project, this Deliverable will be subject to quarterly revisions that will include significant legislative developments and/or the evolution of the Project.

3. Legal Requirements

3.1 General Waste and WEEE regulations

The management of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) in Spain is regulated under Royal Decree 110/2015 (MITECO, RD 110/2015), which transposes the requirements of Directive 2012/19/EU on WEEE (European Commission, WEEE 2012/19/EU) into national law. This regulation establishes obligations for producers, distributors, and waste managers to ensure the proper collection, treatment, and disposal of electronic waste. The main objective is to minimize the environmental impact of WEEE by promoting the circular economy, eco-design, and extended producer responsibility (EPR).

One of the key principles in Spanish WEEE management is extended producer responsibility (EPR), which means that producers of electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) must take responsibility for financing and organizing the collection and treatment of their products at the end of their life cycle. Producers must be registered in the National Integrated Industrial Registry (RII-AEE) and contribute to compliance schemes that oversee proper waste management. Additionally, distributors and retailers must offer take-back systems to facilitate the return of WEEE by consumers, ensuring convenient and free collection points.

The legislation sets specific collection and recycling targets that align with EU directives. For instance, Spain must achieve a collection rate equivalent to 65% of the average weight of EEE placed on the market in the previous three years or 85% of WEEE generated, as established by Directive 2012/19/EU. Treatment facilities must meet strict requirements for depollution, recovery, and material recycling. Hazardous substances such as mercury, lead, and cadmium must be removed and disposed of safely to prevent environmental contamination.

To strengthen compliance, Spain enforces traceability and reporting obligations through digital platforms such as the Electronic Platform for the management of Wastes e-SIR or the specific Electronic Platform for WEEE Management. Producers, collection points, and recyclers must submit periodic reports on the quantities of WEEE generated, collected, treated, and recovered. Regional authorities conduct inspections and impose sanctions in cases of non-compliance, ensuring that illegal disposal and informal recycling practices are minimized.

3.2 Obligations affecting to the different actors

Spanish WEEE Royal Decree (MITECO, RD 110/2015) establishes specific obligations for producers, distributors, waste managers, and public administrations to ensure proper waste management as described in the sections below:

3.2.1 Producers of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (EEE)

Producers are subject to Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) and must:

- Finance and organize WEEE collection and management through individual or collective take-back systems.

- Ensure eco-design compliance, facilitating product repairability, dismantling, and recyclability.
- Register in the National Producer Register and report placed-on-market products and collected WEEE.
- Mark products with the crossed-out wheelie bin symbol, informing users about separate collection obligations.
- Provide information to waste managers regarding product composition to optimize recycling.
- Comply with collection and recovery targets, ensuring a high level of material recovery.
- Develop Waste Prevention plans on a three year basis and present them to the Commission of Coordination on waste matters.

3.2.2 Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) Systems

Individual or collective Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) systems, known in Spain as "Sistemas de Responsabilidad Ampliada del Productor" (SRAP), play a key role in ensuring the proper collection, treatment, and financing of WEEE. Royal Decree 110/2015 (MITECO, RD 110/2015) establishes clear obligations for these systems as summarized below:

- Organization and Financing of WEEE Management
 - Organize and finance the collection, transportation, treatment, and recovery of WEEE generated by the producers they represent.
 - Finance the cost of these operations, including awareness campaigns and administrative costs.
 - Cover collection costs for WEEE from designated collection points, distributors, and municipal waste centers.
- Compliance With Collection and Recycling Targets
 - Collection targets: Defined as a 65% of the average weight of EEE placed on the market by producers participating in the EPR during the three (3) previous years. This target applies per category/fraction of wastes, in this case wastes from Category 4 or Fraction FR4, and per region but is not specific to the particular stream of waste flows.
 - Recycling and recovery targets: Specified in Annex XIV of the decree, requiring high levels of material recovery and hazardous substance removal. Specifically, the minimum targets to be achieved for wastes from Category 4 are:
 - Recovery: 80% by weight of the WEEE managed at treatment facilities.
 - Preparing for reuse and recycling: 75% by weight of the WEEE managed at treatment facilities.
 - Preparing for reuse: 3% by weight of the wastes collected.
- Coordination With Public and Private Collection Networks
 - Sign agreements with local authorities to ensure access to municipal collection points.
 - Work with distributors and retailers to facilitate take-back systems.

- Collaborate with authorized waste managers to guarantee proper treatment and material recovery.
- Ensure transparency in selecting waste managers, applying non-discriminatory and competitive criteria (Annex XVII). The contracting conditions with waste managers must ensure compliance with the principles outlined in Spanish Waste Law (MITECO, Ley 7/2022, s.f.), regarding publicity, competition, and equality, with special emphasis on the application of the proximity principle.
- Reporting and Data Submission Obligations
 - Annual reports on WEEE collection, treatment, and recycling performance.
 - Data on producer compliance, including quantities of EEE placed on the market.
 - Environmental performance indicators, including reuse and recycling rates.
 - Declaration of financial contributions from producers to ensure system sustainability.
- Consumer Awareness and Information
 - Campaigns on separate collection, emphasizing the importance of recycling electronic waste.
 - Clear instructions for consumers on how and where to return WEEE.
 - Collaboration with retailers and municipalities to ensure proper signage and public information.
- Compliance With Authorization and Operational Requirements
 - Obtain authorization from the competent regional authorities.
 - Submit an operational plan detailing WEEE collection, treatment, and financing strategies.
 - Ensure financial guarantees to cover potential environmental liabilities.
 - Undergo regular audits to ensure compliance with obligations and environmental standards.

3.2.3 Distributors and Retailers

Distributors must facilitate WEEE collection and support consumer awareness. Their obligations include:

- Offering free take-back ("old-for-new 1:1 rule"): When selling a new EEE, they must accept an equivalent old device for proper disposal.
- Carrying out collection, storage and transport of WEEE in optimal conditions to facilitate preparing for reuse, recycling and proper containment of hazardous substances.
- Informing consumers about the correct disposal of WEEE.
- Delivering collected WEEE to authorized waste management operators or EPR systems.

- Entering agreements that include preparation for reuse, providing access to the collection facilities, and the necessary means for the separation of WEEE that may be destined for preparation for reuse.
- Reporting to the Electronic Platform for the management of Wastes (e-SIR) or the specific Electronic Platform for WEEE Management.

3.2.4 Consumers and End-Users

Consumers are responsible for ensuring correct disposal of their electronic waste:

- Separating WEEE from household waste and taking it to authorized collection points or returning it to retailers.
- Not discarding WEEE as regular household wastes or in an uncontrolled manner.
- Facilitating reuse: by donating functional devices to authorized reuse centers; or, alternatively when getting rid of it as WEEE, stating in the proof of delivery document whether the condition of the waste is such that it can foreseeably be prepared for reuse.

3.2.5 Waste Management and Treatment Operators

Waste management companies under Royal Decree 110/2015 are responsible for ensuring collection, transport, storage, treatment, preparing for reuse, and disposal of WEEE. Their operations must comply with environmental protection standards and facilitate material recovery, while meeting strict reporting, environmental, and safety obligations. A breakdown of the obligations to all waste management companies handling WEEE is provided below:

- Authorization and Legal Compliance
 - Obtain authorization from the relevant regional authorities before collecting, storing, or treating WEEE.
 - Operate within environmental and safety regulations, preventing pollution and improper handling of hazardous substances.
 - Maintain compliance with European and national waste treatment standards (Annex XIII of RD 110/2015).
- Collection, Transportation, and Storage of WEEE
 - Ensure proper collection and transportation of WEEE from designated collection points, including retailers, municipal centers, and business facilities.
 - Follow specific handling procedures for hazardous components (e.g., batteries, capacitors, and mercury-containing parts).
 - Store WEEE separately based on its category, avoiding contamination that could hinder reuse or recycling.
 - Prevent improper disposal or landfilling of WEEE materials unless no other recovery option is available.
 - Keep records of WEEE movements to ensure traceability.

- Waste Treatment and Recovery. All treatment operations must follow the standards outlined in Annex XIII (MITECO, RD 110/2015) of the decree, which establishes requirements for:
 - Decontamination of WEEE by removing hazardous substances (e.g., refractory fibers containing asbestos).
 - Efficient material separation to maximize the recovery of metals, plastics, and rare earth elements.
 - Prioritization of preparing for reuse over direct recycling or disposal.
 - Avoidance of improper waste treatment, ensuring compliance with environmental and safety standards.
 - Treatment facilities must be designed to minimize emissions, energy consumption, and environmental risks.
- If a waste management company is involved in preparing for reuse, it must:
 - Separate reusable equipment from waste streams at collection and treatment facilities.
 - Conduct checks, cleaning, and repairs to restore WEEE to operating condition.
 - Follow strict quality and safety criteria to guarantee that reused devices do not pose risks to consumers.
 - Ensure that repaired products comply with product safety regulations before reintroducing them to the market.
- Reporting and Traceability. Waste management companies must provide detailed reports to the authorities and extended producer responsibility (EPR) systems, including:
 - Quantities of WEEE collected, treated, and recovered.
 - Destination of recovered materials, specifying whether they were reused, recycled, or disposed of.
 - Compliance with recovery and recycling targets, as set in Annex XIV.
 - Records of hazardous substances removed from the waste stream.

These reports must be submitted annually and made available for inspections.

- Compliance With Recycling and Recovery Target. Waste treatment facilities must meet the minimum recycling and recovery rates outlined in Annex XIV of the decree, such as:
 - Recycling rates: Ensuring a high percentage of WEEE materials are recovered and reintroduced into the economy, specific for different WEEE categories. For instance, for large domestic appliances, a minimum of 80% by weight of the waste input will be recovered (prepared for reuse or recycled).
- Cooperation With EPR Systems and Authorities:
 - Work with EPR systems (SRAP) to ensure efficient WEEE management.
 - Allow inspections and audits from regulatory authorities and EPR organizations.
 - Share data on WEEE flows and treatment processes, ensuring transparency.
 - Follow fair competition rules when contracting with EPR systems (Annex XVII).

- Environmental and Safety Standards
 - Prevent pollution and improper emissions, using best available techniques (BAT) for waste treatment.
 - Ensure worker safety when handling hazardous WEEE components.
 - Follow strict storage conditions to avoid contamination or fire risks.

3.3 Waste classification (EWC and LER-RAEE) of wastes from kitchen hobs

The wastes that will be managed as part of the Project will be primarily wastes from cooking hobs, either of ceramic or induction hobs, are classified in Spanish (MITECO, RD 110/2015) and European regulations (European Commission, WEEE 2012/19/EU) as Wastes from Category 4 equipment (large equipment with a dimension higher than 50 cm) and more specifically household or domestic wastes within this Category. Since this type of wastes are almost in its totality non-hazardous, meaning they do not contain dangerous substances, the corresponding code in line with European Waste Catalogue (European Commission 2000/532/EC2) that apply to the waste management operations according to Table 1 of Royal Decree 110/2015 (MITECO, RD 110/2015) is LER-RAEE 200136-42.

However, in some limited instances, asbestos containing ceramic fibers could be present in very old equipment. In this case, the waste management company should reclassify these wastes to hazardous wastes of the Category 4 with the LER-RAEE code 200135-41* and only perform waste management operations if their authorization includes the management of these types of wastes.

Other potential wastes that eventually could also be included within the scope of the Project such as washing machines or dishwashers fall under the same Category of Products and share the same LER-RAEE code 200136-42.

As a result of the treatment of the kitchen hobs waste in preparing for reuse centers, the following output are produced:

- Recovered components for reuse (products): glass plates, PCBs and induction coils.
- Recovered materials to recycle (wastes):
 - Printed Circuit Boards, Wires, Coils, Glass wastes: LER 160216
 - Plastics wastes: LER 191204
 - Metal wastes: LER 191202 (iron and steel) and LER 191203 (aluminum & copper)

3.4 End-of-life related Ecodesign requirements

Both the Spanish Waste Law (MITECO, Ley 7/2022, s.f.) and the Royal Decree 110/2015 (MITECO, RD 110/2015) introduce design obligations for electrical and electronic products to minimize waste generation and facilitate sustainable waste management. These regulations align with EU Circular Economy policies, particularly the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (European Commission, ESPR) and digital product passports (European Commission, DPP, 2024) for electrical and electronic equipment.

Key end-of-life related ecodesign requirements can be summarized as follows:

- Manufacturers must ensure that products are designed for durability, repairability, and recyclability.
 - Disassembly and Recycling: Products must be designed to facilitate disassembly, material sorting, and recovery processes, thereby enhancing recyclability and reducing environmental impact at the end of their lifecycle.
 - Standardization for disassembly and repair: Products should allow for easy dismantling, part replacement, and maintenance, supporting repair and refurbishment industries.
 - Manufacturers must prioritize waste prevention by designing products that are durable, repairable, and upgradeable.
 - Availability of spare parts: Manufacturers must ensure that replacement parts and repair instructions are accessible to authorized repairers and reuse centers.
 - The use of modular components should be promoted to extend product life and facilitate component replacement.
 - Design for automated disassembly: Newer electronics should support robotic disassembly to improve recycling efficiency.
- Marking of materials: Plastics, metals, and electronic components should be labeled to facilitate material separation during recycling as well as the presence and the location of hazardous/substances of concern within the product, if any.
- Product labeling and consumer information: Manufacturers shall provide clear information on product lifespan, repairability, and disposal instructions to facilitate reuse and recycling.

It is expected that the upcoming Digital Product Passport (DPP) framework will further enforce eco-design transparency, enhance end to end traceability of a product throughout its value chain and make information available to actors involved during its lifecycle including the end of life, ensuring that waste management data is embedded in the products put on the European market. Some of these key requirements are described in more detail in the sections below.

3.4.1 Prevention of Obsolescence

In Spain, the prevention of obsolescence in electrical and electronic products is both in the Waste Law (MITECO, Ley 7/2022, s.f.) and in the RD 110/2015 (MITECO, RD 110/2015). Waste Law 07/2022 emphasizes waste prevention and sets a general target to reduce waste generation by 13% by 2025 and 15% by 2030. Among one of the measures to achieve these targets it forbids the destruction or disposal by landfill of unsold surpluses of non-perishable products such as electrical appliances, among others, is prohibited, unless such products must be destroyed in accordance with other regulations or for consumer protection and safety. Such surpluses shall first be destined to reuse channels, including donation, and when this is not possible, to preparation for reuse or to the options foreseen in the waste hierarchy. Furthermore, it encourages measures that extend the useful life of products, including electrical and electronic equipment (EEE). This includes promoting repairability, reuse, and the reduction of hazardous substances in product design.

More specifically, RD 110/2015 on WEEE states that by involving the manufacturer in the financing of waste management, it is expected that better designs of EEE will be incentivized that facilitate their disassembly, repair or recycling or increase their useful life (avoiding planned obsolescence).

3.4.2 Waste Prevention Plans by Producers

Under Spain's Royal Decree 110/2015, producers of electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) are mandated to develop triennial Waste Prevention Plans aimed at minimizing the generation of waste from such devices. As specified in Article 6.4 of Royal Decree 110/2015 (MITECO, RD 110/2015) this obligation applies to producers with a market share exceeding 0.1% in any EEE category are required to formulate and present these plans and their progress to the National Commission for the Coordination on Wastes on a triennial basis.

While the decree does not prescribe a specific format, the plans should detail the preventive measures the producer will undertake to reduce waste generation. This includes strategies for:

- Extending Product Lifespan: Designing products that are durable and have a longer useful life.
- Facilitating Reuse and Repair: Ensuring products can be easily disassembled, repaired, and reassembled.
- Reducing Hazardous Substances: Minimizing the use of materials that are harmful to the environment or human health.
- Enhancing Recyclability: Designing products in a way that simplifies the recycling process at the end of their lifecycle.

3.4.3 End-of-life considerations in Digital Product Passports (DPP)

The Digital Product Passport (DPP) (European Commission, DPP, 2024) is a key initiative under the EU Circular Economy Action Plan and the Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (European Commission, ESPR). It aims to provide comprehensive product data to improve resource efficiency, repairability, and recyclability across a product's life cycle.

DPP will be implemented in phases with certain products like industrial, light transport means and electric vehicle batteries requiring DPPs by 2027. Afterwards other household products, including EEE will follow, with specific timelines and requirements to be detailed in forthcoming regulations.

The primary goal of integrating DPPs into these products is to enhance transparency, traceability, and sustainability throughout their lifecycle. By providing detailed information on material composition, manufacturing processes, and end-of-life handling, DPPs aim (a.o.) to:

- Facilitate maintenance, reuse and repair by offering access to component specifications and repair guides.
 - The DPP will store repair and maintenance instructions, making it easier for consumers and professionals to extend product life.
 - Access to compatible spare parts and refurbishment guidelines will support the preparing for reuse.
- Promote recycling and proper disposal by detailing material constituents and hazardous substances.
 - The DPP will include detailed information on material composition, including critical raw materials (e.g., rare earth elements in electronics). This will help recyclers identify valuable components and improve material recovery processes.

- The passport will provide standardized disposal instructions based on EU waste codes (e.g., LER-RAEEWC codes for WEEE) will promote the development of Treatment Guidelines.
- It will help waste operators correctly sort and process electronic waste, batteries, and hazardous materials.
- Allow regulators and waste managers to track the flow of used products and components, ensuring they reach authorized treatment and recovery facilities.
 - This will help prevent illegal exports of e-waste and improve compliance with WEEE Directive targets.
- Increase consumer awareness and responsible disposal. By scanning a product's DPP (via QR code or NFC chip), users will receive clear disposal recommendations, directing them to authorized take-back or collection points. This is expected to increase collection rates and encourage proper waste segregation.
- Enhance traceability and showcase the circular origin of products and components recovered from WEEE in preparing for re-use centres:
 - Currently there is not a Delegated Act stating the specific requirements for DPP for these recovered electronic appliances and components. But it is foreseeable that recovered products and components put on the market will be required to have their own DPP, as it is already regulated for batteries repurposed or remanufactured (art. 7.7. Regulation EU 2023/1542, concerning batteries and waste batteries).

3.4.4 Repairability

The European Union has established a robust regulatory framework to enhance the repairability of electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) as part of its broader strategy for sustainability and circular economy. The key objective is to extend product lifespans, reduce electronic waste, and minimize environmental impacts. These requirements are primarily set through the Ecodesign Directive) (European Commission 2009/125/EC, 2009) and related regulations, which impose obligations on manufacturers to improve product reparability, durability, and resource efficiency. Specific Ecodesign regulations now mandate that manufacturers provide access to spare parts and repair information for certain categories of products, including household appliances.

One of the main legal instruments supporting repairability is the Right to Repair, which has been progressively introduced into EU law, leading to the Directive EU 2024/1799 on common rules promoting the repair of goods which obliges manufacturers to repair those goods, upon consumer`s request, under the list in Annex II of Union legal acts laying down repairability requirements:

In addition, WEEE Directive (European Commission, WEEE 2012/19/EU) and Spanish RD on WEEE (MITECO, RD 110/2015) indirectly support repairability by encouraging the reuse and refurbishment of electronic devices.

Spain has also introduced legal provisions aimed at making repairs more accessible and affordable. The General Law for the Defense of Consumers and Users (Ministerio de la Presidencia, 2020) strengthens consumer rights by requiring that repairs be offered as a first option before replacement under warranty claims. Additionally, the law extends the legal warranty period for new electronic products from two to three years, and manufacturers must guarantee the availability of technical support and spare parts for at least ten years after a product leaves the market. These measures aim to discourage premature product obsolescence and encourage a culture of repair.

To further promote repairability, Spain is considering initiatives similar to France's Repairability Index described below, although no mandatory scoring system is yet in place.

3.4.4.1 France: Durability Index and Repair bonus

Within the European Union France has taken a pioneering role in strengthening repairability requirements for electrical and electronic equipment. and has gone further by implementing specific national laws to enhance product longevity and consumer access to repairs. These measures aim to reduce electronic waste, promote circular economy practices, and empower consumers with better information about the repairability of their devices.

One of France's most significant initiatives is the Repairability Index, introduced by the Anti-Waste for a Circular Economy Law (France AGECE, 2020). This index, mandatory since January 2021, requires manufacturers to label certain electronic products including washing machines with a score (from 0 to 10) reflecting their repairability. The score is based on several criteria, including the availability of spare parts, ease of disassembly, availability of repair manuals, and the price of spare parts relative to the product cost. This measure aims to increase transparency and encourage consumers to choose more repairable products. Although this is not yet an obligation applying to kitchen hobs it is expected to be covered by this obligation in the near future.

Additionally, France has strengthened obligations for manufacturers regarding spare parts availability. Under the AGECE Law, producers must ensure that essential spare parts remain available for a specified duration after a product is placed on the market. In some cases, manufacturers are also required to provide these parts at a reasonable price and within a limited delivery time to facilitate efficient repairs. Furthermore, a new law passed in 2023 extends these requirements, progressively transitioning the Repairability Index into a Durability Index by 2024 (Figure 1), incorporating additional factors like product robustness and software update policies.

Figure 1: Examples of Durability indexes (France, 2024) ¹

¹ Durability indexes (France, 2024): <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/politiques-publiques/indice-reparabilite>

France also offers financial incentives to promote repair over replacement. A government-backed fund, known as the “Repair Bonus” (France - Bonus Réparation, 2022) introduced in December 2022, provides subsidies for consumers who choose to repair certain products instead of discarding them. Discounts of 10 to 45 euros are available for repairs conducted by certified professionals, covering kitchen jobs along with other items like washing machines. This initiative helps lower repair costs and supports the development of a stronger repair industry.

3.5 End-of-life Management. Collection and Treatment Requirements

Waste management operational requirements to take into consideration are summarized in the following section. In any case, this should only be considered as a guide and any waste management operation shall only be performed by actors holding the required authorizations and in compliance with the conditions established in these authorizations and in the applicable national, regional or local regulations.

3.5.1 Collection of WEEE

For non-Hazardous of the Category 4 WEEE (LER-RAEE 200136-42) these are the major requirements under Spanish legislation (MITECO, RD 110/2015) for collection activities.

Producers, distributors, and municipal authorities share responsibility for ensuring the proper collection of Category 4 WEEE:

- Producers must establish and finance systems for the collection of WEEE through authorized compliance schemes (SCRAP) or individual collection systems.
- Distributors and Retailers must provide free take-back systems for consumers when they purchase equivalent new products (old-for-new 1:1 collection).
- Municipalities must provide designated collection points (Puntos Limpios) where households can dispose of WEEE free of charge. These points must be integrated with producer responsibility organizations to ensure proper handling and reporting.
- Collection points should obtain a Environmental Identification Number (NIMA or *Número de Identificación Medioambiental*) to be able to document properly the shipments of wastes. Although it may not be an obligation in all Regions (*Comunidades Autónomas*) for non-hazardous wastes it is a requirement in some of them and therefore it is recommended to obtain such a NIMA. In order to do that, they should register as *small* waste holders (P05) and/or waste generators (P02) with the respective regional environmental authorities or agencies (see Annex I).

Collection points and logistics providers must:

- Ensure that large appliances are not broken or dismantled before arriving at treatment facilities to maximize recovery.
- Store WEEE in weatherproof conditions to prevent water infiltration and exposure to environmental factors and over an impermeable flooring to contain spills
- Include in the collection facilities spaces and means for separate collection of WEEE that may be destined for preparing for reuse,

- Keep records of collected waste volumes and destinations to comply with traceability requirements using the e-SIR electronic platform (or equivalent regional platform as described in section Shipment and transportation of WEEE)

3.5.2 Shipment and transportation of WEEE

Royal Decree regulating the shipments and transportations of wastes within the Spanish territory (MITECO RD 553/2020, 2020) establish the documentation requirements for the transportation wastes in Spain. Key requirements for the non-hazardous wastes subject to this Project include:

- Environmental Identification Number (NIMA): Waste producers generating non-hazardous waste above 1,000 tons per year must obtain a NIMA for each collection or generation center. This identifier is essential for electronic processing of waste shipment documentation. Although, for smaller generation quantities it may not be an obligation in all Regions (*Comunidades Autónomas*) it is a requirement in some of them and therefore it is highly recommended that collection points register as *small* waste holders (P05) and/or waste generators (P02) and obtain such a NIMA. Annex I shows a list of the links to the web pages of the different regional Governments (*Comunidades Autónomas*) where the application to obtain these NIMAs can be performed.
- Waste Treatment Contract: Prior to any shipment, a document of acceptance (in Spanish, *Contrato de Tratamiento*) to be signed between the waste producer (or holder) and the authorized waste management company that receives the waste is mandatory. This contract should detail:
 - Identification and location of the origin of the waste and the destination facilities.
 - Estimated quantity of waste to be transferred.
 - Identification of the waste using the appropriate European Waste Catalogue (EWC) code, in this case LER-RAEE 200136-42.
 - Planned frequency of shipments.
 - Specified treatment method for the waste.
 - Other relevant information to ensure proper waste treatment.
 - Legal consequences for non-compliance with the contract terms.
- Identification Document: For each shipment, an identification document must be completed before transportation begins. This document, which accompanies the waste during transit, includes:
 - Details of the waste, including its EWC code and quantity.
 - Information about the origin and destination facilities.
 - Identification of the treatment method in the destination facilities.
 - Contact information for the transporter.

Upon delivery, the recipient facility verifies and signs the document, confirming receipt and acceptance of the waste. All parties involved—producer, transporter, and recipient—must retain copies of this document for at least three (3) years. Adherence to these documentation requirements ensures traceability, accountability, and environmentally sound management of non-hazardous waste during transportation within Spain.

All this documentation must be processed electronically through e-SIR electronic platform developed by Spanish Ministry for the Environmental Transition (MITECO) and in some cases through the similar platforms established by some Regional Governments (*Comunidades Autónomas*).

Table 1 shows the latest status at the date of issuance of this Deliverable of the electronic platforms to be used for the intra-regional or inter-regional waste movements.

PROCEDIMIENTO PARA EL TRASLADO DE RESIDUOS		
CCAA	INTER-CCAA	INTRA-CA
Andalucía	SIRA	
Aragón	eSIR	Calidad Ambiental Aragón - PDR
Asturias	eSIR	
Baleares, Islas	eSIR	SINGER
Canarias, Islas	eSIR	
Cantabria	eSIR	
Castilla y León	eSIR	EDCS
Castilla La Mancha	eSIR	
Cataluña	eSIR	SDR
Comunidad Valenciana	eSIR	ADCR
Extremadura	eSIR	
Galicia	GAIA	
Madrid, Comunidad de	eSIR	
Murcia, Región de	eSIR	
Navarra, Comunidad Foral de	eSIR	navarra.es
País Vasco	eSIR	IKS-INGURUNET
Rioja, La	eSIR	
Ceuta	eSIR	
Melilla	eSIR	

Table 1 Electronic platforms for the processing of waste shipment documentation requirements in Spain in Spain (MITECO 2023).²

More specifically, the links to the specific platforms to be used in the regions where the Preparing for Reuse Centers (CPRs or Centros de Preparación para la Reutilización in Spanish) participating in Life WEELOOP Project are located, are provided below:

- Andalucía: Regional Platform SIRA for both intra-regional or shipments from other regions: <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/portal/areas-tematicas/residuos-suelos-contaminados-economia-circular/gestion-de-residuos/traslado-residuos/procedimiento-electronico-traslado-residuos-real-decreto-553-2020->
- País Vasco (Basque Region): e-SIR (recently migrated from the former platform IKS-Ingurunet): <https://servicio.mapama.gob.es/esir-web-adv/>

Further to these documentation requirements, transportation of wastes must be performed by waste shipment companies with proper authorizations to perform these operations and meeting technical and safety requirements. In particular, stowage and securing of goods in road transportation are

² Note: País Vasco and Navarra have also adopted e-SIR platform

governed by Royal Decree 563/2017, which aligns with the European Directive 2014/47/EU must be met, This regulation mandates that all cargo must be secured to prevent movement during transit, thereby ensuring the safety of the driver, vehicle, and other road users. Proper stowage should prevent the load from sliding, tilting, swaying, deforming, or rotating. To achieve this, methods such as blocking, locking, or lashing are employed, often in combination. The decree also specifies technical standards, including the number and capacity of lashing straps, and requires that vehicles undergo regular inspections to verify compliance.

3.5.3 Recovery Operations: Preparing for Reuse (Treatment code R14)

This preparing for reuse of Category 4 WEEE (large household appliances such as washing machines, dishwashers, and kitchen hobs) is a key priority in Royal Decree 110/2015, which transposes Directive 2012/19/EU on WEEE into Spanish law. The aim is to extend product life cycles, reduce environmental impact, and promote the circular economy by maximizing the reuse of functional components and appliances.

In any case, Preparing for Reuse is considered a waste Management operation of recovery as defined in article 2 of Waste Law 07/2022 (MITECO, Ley 7/2022, s.f.)³. Therefore the preparation of reuse of products or components such as induction devices or glass parts that are object of Life WEELOOP Project must be performed at CPRs authorized to perform these operations (Recovery operation “R14 00” as outlined in Annex XVI of Royal Decree 110/2015). Specific legal requirements applying to preparation for reuse operations include:

- Obligation to use CPR fully authorized to perform preparing for reuse operations.
- Facilities must also comply with technical requirements and quality standards for repaired and refurbished products.
- Selection and Inspection Criteria. Before undergoing preparing for reuse, WEEE must be assessed to determine its feasibility for repair, refurbishment, or component recovery:
 - Appliances must be mechanically intact and free from severe structural damage.
 - Equipment must not contain hazardous substances that prevent safe reuse.
 - When preparing for reuse complete appliances, electrical and functional tests must confirm that components (e.g., motors, wiring, electronic controls) can be safely repaired or replaced.
- Reconditioning and Repair Procedures: Annex XIII of RD 110/2015 outlines specific preparation steps that authorized facilities must follow when preparing for reuse of complete appliances is performed:
 - Cleaning and disinfection of the appliance.
 - Replacement of defective components with original or equivalent parts.
 - Software updates or reprogramming (if applicable).
 - Testing of electrical and mechanical functions to meet safety standards.

³ Preparing for reuse: "The recovery operation consisting of checking, cleaning, or repairing, by which products or components of products that have become waste are prepared so that they can be reused without any other prior transformation and cease to be considered waste if they meet the applicable product standards of a technical and consumer nature.

- Certification and Warranty for Reused Appliances. Appliances resulting from preparation for reuse must comply with technical and safety standards, including CE marking if they are placed back on the market.
 - Products must come with a minimum warranty period, as required by Spanish consumer protection laws.
 - Operators must maintain records of repaired and resold appliances, ensuring traceability and compliance with reuse targets.

Hence, complete appliances and components recovered from WEEE cease to be waste after being treated in preparing for reuse centres, so that they are reintroduced in the economy as products that ought to comply with the laws applicable to them.

Furthermore, certain materials recycled from WEEE might cease to be waste as well provided that the treatment plant fulfils the recovery process and the material complies with the provisions set out in Article 6, End-of-waste status of Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste and Article 5 of the Spanish Waste Law (MITECO, Ley 7/2022) for the end-of-waste condition (in spanish, fin de la condición de residuo).

3.5.4 Treatment requirements: Recycling (Treatment Code R 12)

Although in many other European Union (EU) Member States (MSs) WEEE Management regulation refers to the CENELEC 50625 family of WEEE related standards (CENELEC 50625) , in Spain the treatment requirements for Category 4 WEEE (large electronic appliances, e.g., waste hobs, washing machines, dishwashers, etc..) are detailed in part A to F and G1 of Annex XIII of Royal Decree 110/2015 (MITECO, RD 110/2015), that establish specific procedures for depollution, material recovery, and environmental protection during treatment operations. Additionally, a Technical Note summarizing the technical requirements to be met by treatment facilities has been published by the Ministry of Environment (MITECO, Nota Técnica Requisitos Técnicos de Tratamiento).

A summary of the treatment requirements applicable to the treatment of non-hazardous wastes from Category 4 equipment or Fraction FR4 as shown in Figure 2 is provided below:

Figure 2: Generic recycling process for FR4 non wastes

- Authorized Treatment Facilities and Compliance Requirements
 - Treatment of Category 4 non-hazardous WEEE must take place in authorized waste treatment facilities that comply with environmental and safety regulations. Facilities must hold integrated environmental authorization or a waste management permit issued by the relevant regional authority allowing them to perform R1202 Dismantling operations, R1203 Separation of components including the removal of hazardous substances or components and/or R1205 Mechanical fragmentation or fragmentation prior to further treatment, as outlined in Annex XVI of RD 110/2015.
 - Operators must ensure proper documentation, traceability, and reporting through the e-SIR electronic platform, including details on the amounts processed, fractions recovered, and final destinations of recovered materials.
- Depollution and Component Removal
 - Although LER-RAEE 200136-42 is classified as non-hazardous, treatment facilities must still follow strict depollution procedures to maximize recycling and recovery, and in the case of waste hobs particularly dismantling of components that may contain hazardous substances (e.g., ceramic refractory fibers containing asbestos).
 - Ensuring that reusable components (motors, wiring, plastic parts) are extracted intact whenever feasible.
- Material Separation and Processing. After depollution, treatment facilities must separate different material fractions to maximize recycling efficiency:
 - Metals (ferrous and non-ferrous) must be extracted using magnetic and eddy current separators.

- Plastics must be sorted to remove halogenated compounds and facilitate high-quality recycling.
- Glass components (if present) must be handled separately to prevent contamination.
- Electronic circuit boards and external wires should be processed in specialized facilities to recover valuable materials.
- Recycling and Recovery Targets. Annex XIII mandates that Category 4 WEEE must meet minimum material recovery and recycling rates.
 - 85% of the total weight of collected Category 4 WEEE must be recovered.
 - 80% of the total weight must be specifically recycled or prepared for reuse.

Operators must provide annual reports based on mass balances performed verifying compliance. Companies failing to meet recycling and recovery targets may face additional corrective measures imposed by regulatory bodies.

- Environmental and Occupational Health protection measures
 - Treatment operations must prevent dust emissions, noise pollution, and improper handling of residues.
 - Workers must use protective equipment and follow safety protocols to prevent exposure to residual contaminants.
 - Facilities must have contingency plans for fire prevention, spills, and accidental releases of substances.

Non-compliance with treatment regulations can result in administrative sanctions, including fines, suspension of operations, or legal action.

3.5.5 Traceability Requirements

Further to the use of e-SIR or analogous regional electronic platforms as described in section 3.5.2, Spanish RD 110/2015, contemplated the need to register all waste management operations in a common electronic platform for the management of WEEE (or Plataforma electrónica de gestión de RAEE in Spanish). This electronic WEEE management platform (MITECO, 2018) was further developed in Ministerial Order TED/1032/2024 (MITECO, 2024) that established the obligation of registering WEEE Management operations and entered into force on 2 January 2025 (although the electronic ICT platform actually entered into operation effectively on 2 February 2025)

In line with the principles of administrative simplification and telematic processing in public administrations, this platform is intended to act as a single database on the collection and treatment of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) and will be fed by the operators who collect or receive WEEE for the first time and by the managers who treat it. This should guarantee the control and traceability of WEEE, since the platform will be the means through which managers comply with their information obligations such as maintaining the chronological file and the annual report.

The electronic WEEE management ICT platform will collect information on the collection and management of WEEE in each autonomous community and at the national level. The use of a single platform should create a single source of WEEE collection and management data, and avoid certain distortions generated by the multiplicity of platforms. Likewise, it should facilitate the control surveillance of WEEE data and its management by public administrations.

A particular feature of the traceability system established by the WEEE management ICT platform is the obligation to tag the WEEE with labels that allow its electronic reading (QR code). These labels are generated directly by the ICT platform although it is expected and desirable its compatibility with existing systems that some extended responsibility schemes have already in place.

This Ministerial Order defines deadlines for Individual Labeling of WEEE by collection Category of fraction. For the wastes from category 4 where the wastes from kitchen hobs are included, it defines the following timeframes:

- Collective labeling during the first two years from the Order's effective date (until 1 January 2027)
- Individual labeling obligation will apply from the second year after the order entered into force, therefore from 2 January 2027. However, voluntary individual labeling may be implemented voluntarily from the date of entry into force.

From the date of entry into force of this Order, the different operators are required to join progressively the electronic platform according to this calendar:

- WEEE waste management companies and preparing-for-reuse centers: From the date of entry into force (January 22025), although the electronic ICT platform entered effectively in operation on 3 February 2025)
- Distributors of EEE: Within six months after the order enters into force (by 2 July 2025).
- Local entities: Within six months after the order enters into force, ensuring that their collection facilities comply with the requirements (by 2 July 2025).

4. Summary

This document provides a summary of the legislative requirements related to the management of end-of-life EEE products, and particularly of waste from kitchen hobs. Not only waste management regulations of operational type are addressed (e.g. collection, shipments or treatment operations) but also those pertaining to other areas of the life cycle of these products that impact the end-of-life phase, more specifically eco-design and the life of the products.

In any case, this document should be considered just as a Guidance Document on the legal requirements identified, Therefore, it does not replace or supersede official legal texts, which remain the authoritative sources. Organizations must ensure compliance with all applicable laws and regulations or with the conditions of their Authorizations by consulting the relevant documents. Furthermore, it can not cover all particular cases that can be faced in the management of EEE and WEEE during the execution of the Project.

Disclaimer

The information contained in this document is provided in good faith and for general guidance only. No liability is accepted by the author or by the WEELOOP consortium or any of its members for any errors, omissions, or misinterpretations. Users are advised to refer to the full legal texts and seek professional legal advice where necessary.

Annex I: Web pages from Regional Governments (Comunidades Autónomas) where NIMAs required for waste collections and shipments can be obtained

Andalucía: <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/sira-buscador-publico/>

Aragón : <http://calidadambiental.aragon.es/ia/estadisticasresiduos.aspx?id=4>

Asturias: <http://www.medioambiente.asturias.org/IASERVICIOSRESIDUOS/Buscar/BuscarInstalacion>

Baleares, Islas : <http://residus.caib.es/regpig/>

Canarias, Islas: [https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/medioambiente/materias/residuos/registro-de-https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/medioambiente/materias/residuos/registro-de-produccion/buscador-de-productores/produccion/buscador-de-productores/](https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/medioambiente/materias/residuos/registro-dehttps://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/medioambiente/materias/residuos/registro-de-produccion/buscador-de-productores/produccion/buscador-de-productores/)

Cantabria: <https://siacan.cantabria.es/siacan/publico/PrepareBuscadorEmpresasProductoresView.do>

Castilla – La Mancha: <https://ireno.castillalamancha.es/forms/geref000.htm>

Castilla y León: <https://servicios.jcyl.es/gaser/verFrmBuscadorNimas.action>

Cataluña: <http://sdr.arc.cat/sdr/ListNimas.do>

Comunidad Valenciana: https://residuos.gva.es/res_buscaweb/buscador_residuos_avanzado.aspx

Extremadura: http://extremambiente.juntaex.es/index.php?option=com_content&id=2563

Galicia: <https://sirga.xunta.gal/nima>

Madrid: http://gestiona.madrid.org/pcea_nima_web/html/web/InicioAccion.icm

Murcia: <https://caamext.carm.es/calaweb/faces/faces/vista/seleccionNima.jsp>

Navarra: <https://extra.navarra.es/InformacionPublicaPRTR/RPGR.html#/PGR>

País Vasco: <https://www.euskadi.eus/informacion/registro-de-produccion-y-gestionhttps://www.euskadi.eus/informacion/registro-de-produccion-y-gestion-de-residuos/web01-a2inghon/es/de-residuos/web01-a2inghon/es/>

La Rioja: <https://www.larioja.org/medio-ambiente/es/residuos/buscador-nimas>

Ceuta: <https://www.ceuta.es/ceuta/residuos>

Melilla: https://www.melilla.es/melillaPortal/contenedor.jsp?seccion=s_fdes_d4_v1.jsp&conteni

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CPR: Centros de Preparación para la Reutilización (in english, Preparing for Reuse Centers)

DPP: Digital Product Passport

e-SIR: Electronic platform for the Management of Wastes

EWC: European Waste Catalogue

EEE: Electrical and Electronic Equipment

EPR: Extended Producer Responsibility

ICT: Information and Communication Technologies based system

LER: Lista Europea de Residuos (in english; European Waste Code)

LER-RAEE: Lista Europea de Residuos – Residuos de Aparatos Eléctricos y Electrónicos (In english: European Waste Code – Wastes from Electrical and Electronic Equipment)

MITECO: Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico (In english, Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the the Demographic Challenge)

R Code: Waste management code referring to annex II ‘Recovery operations’ of the Waste Framework Directive and of Spanish Royal Decree on Wastes.

RAEE: Residuos de Aparatos Eléctricos y Electrónicos (In english: Wastes from electrical and Electronic Equipment)

RD: Royal Decree

SRAP: Sistema de Responsabilidad Ampliada del Productor (in english:

SCRAP: Sistema Colectivo de Responsabilidad Ampliada del Productor (in english: Colective Extended Producer Responsibility System)

SRAP: Sistema de Responsabilidad Ampliada del Productor (in english: Extended Producer Responsibility System)

WEEE: Wastes from Electrical and Electronic Equipment

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